

SIMILAR AND DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF FAIRY TALES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotatsiya: Ertaklar — bu har bir millatning madaniyati, tarixi va qadriyatlarini aks ettiruvchi muhim adabiy janrdir. Ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi ertaklar ham o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib, ularning o'xshash va turli tomonlari mavjud. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek ertaklarining o'xshashliklari va farqlari, ularning mazmuni, strukturasidagi o'ziga xosliklar, qahramonlar, mavzular va axloqiy saboqlar haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ertaklar, ingliz tili, maqollar, axloqiy saboqlar, xalq og'zaki ijodi, urf-odatlar, tarix.

Аннотация: Сказки – важный литературный жанр, отражающий культуру, историю и ценности каждого народа. Сказки на английском и узбекском языках имеют свои особенности, имеют схожие и разные аспекты. В данной статье представлена информация о сходстве и различиях английских и узбекских сказок, их содержании, структуре, персонажах, темах и нравственных уроках.

Ключевые слова: сказки, английский язык, пословицы, уроки нравственности, фольклор, традиции, история.

Abstract: Fairy tales are an important literary genre that reflects the culture, history and values of each nation. Fairy tales in English and Uzbek have their own characteristics, and they have similar and different aspects. This article provides information on the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek fairy tales, their content, structure, characters, themes, and moral lessons.

Key words: fairy tales, English language, proverbs, moral lessons, folklore, traditions, history.

INTRODUCTION

Fairy tales are mainly for children and contain fantastical events, characters and lessons to be learned. There are many similarities between English and Uzbek fairy tales. For example, in both cultures, moral lessons are taught through fairy tales, the struggle of heroes against evil forces, and the struggle between good and evil. Such common features increase the international importance of fairy tales and bring them closer to each other.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In English and Uzbek fairy tales, the heroes are often ordinary people or animals. They often fight against evil forces and overcome difficulties to achieve their goals. In English fairy tales, such as Little Red Riding Hood or Gulliver's Travels, characters often discover new worlds for themselves. In Uzbek fairy tales, such as "Alisher Navoi" or "Farhod and Shirin", the heroes often try to protect the values of their people. Heroes in Uzbek fairy tales often reflect the customs and traditions of the people. They learn moral lessons, including love of country, patriotism and justice. In English fairy tales, the characters focus more on individualism and personal success. This difference comes from the unique values and traditions of each culture. The themes and motifs of fairy tales have similar and different aspects. English fairy tales often feature magic, fantasy, and adventure. For example, fairy tales such as "The Adventures of Seven Girls" or "The Hidden Girl" contain magical elements. These themes expand children's imaginations and introduce them to new worlds. Uzbek fairy tales reflect more folk traditions, customs and historical events. For example, fairy tales such as "The Red Girl" or "The Cradle" reflect the historical figures, customs and traditions of their people. These topics help children learn about the history and culture of their people. One of the most important aspects of fairy tales is moral

lessons. English and Uzbek fairy tales also teach moral lessons, but their content and effect are different. English fairy tales often explore values such as personal success, friendship, loyalty, and courage. For example, in the fairy tale "The Red-Headed Girl", the heroine learns to be loyal to her friends, fight against evil forces, and protect herself.[1]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Moral lessons in Uzbek fairy tales include values such as folk traditions, patriotism, justice and friendship. For example, in the fairy tale "Shirin and Moshgul", the heroes learn the lessons of protecting their people, restoring justice and fighting evil. These lessons help children to respect and follow the values of their people. There are also differences in the structure of English and Uzbek fairy tales. English fairy tales often clearly show the stages of beginning, development and ending. They are often short and simple and attract children's attention. Uzbek fairy tales often have longer and more detailed stories. They focus more on visual and spiritual aspects, which help children to better understand the culture of their people. Uzbek fairy tales often use poetic expressions, proverbs and elements of folklore. This makes fairy tales more attractive and interesting. English fairy tales use more modern language and expressions, which helps children understand fairy tales more easily.[2]

Fairy tales are important works of art that reflect the culture and history of every nation. The differences in their structure and structure show the way of thinking, values and traditions of different peoples. We will consider the differences in the structure of English and Uzbek fairy tales. Despite the fact that the beginning, development and ending of fairy tales have many similarities, they also have their own characteristics. English fairy tales are often characterized by a simple and clear beginning. In these tales, the characters and the setting are introduced quickly, and the problem or problematic situation appears immediately. During the development phase, the characters go on adventures to solve problems, showing difficulties and

obstacles in the process. In the finale, the problem is solved, the heroes win, or a lesson is learned.[3]

Uzbek fairy tales are more detailed and descriptive, and have a beginning related to customs and traditions. These tales often begin in a historical context or based on the values of the people. During the development phase, the characters face internal struggles and spiritual challenges. In Uzbek fairy tales, events are described in more detail, which allows readers to understand the emotions of the characters in a deeper way. And the ending often emphasizes the loyalty of the heroes to their people, traditions and values. In terms of imagery, English fairy tales are usually simple and clearly expressed, aiming to attract children's attention. They are short and easy to understand, events develop quickly. Uzbek fairy tales are written in a more descriptive and poetic style. They are enriched with proverbs, folklore and figurative expressions, which make the fairy tales more attractive. In Uzbek fairy tales, the events are often described in detail, which allows readers to enter the events more deeply. In terms of characters, characters in English fairy tales often have individualistic characteristics and struggle to achieve their personal goals. They go through a process of change and development, but these processes are usually shown quickly and simply. In Uzbek fairy tales, heroes are more connected with folk traditions, customs and values. They often fight to protect the interests of their people, and this process is more related to internal and spiritual development. In terms of themes and motifs, English fairy tales are often associated with fantasy, magic, and adventure, with fast-moving events. They focus more on personal success. Uzbek fairy tales contain more historical, cultural and moral themes. They are related to national traditions, values and customs, and help children learn about the history and culture of their people. [4]

Thus, differences in the structure of fairy tales are expressed through their content, characters, plot, and moral lessons. English fairy tales focus more on individualism

and fiction, while Uzbek fairy tales focus on folk traditions and historical values. These differences reflect the unique culture and values of each nation.[5]

CONCLUSION

Fairy tales in English and Uzbek languages have their own characteristics, and there are similarities and differences between them. In both cultures, moral lessons, the struggle of heroes against evil forces, and the struggle between good and evil are reflected in fairy tales. However, there are differences in terms of characters, themes, motives, and moral lessons. English fairy tales reflect personal success and fiction, and Uzbek fairy tales reflect more folk traditions and historical events. Fairy tales reflect the culture and values of each nation. They help children learn about the history, customs and traditions of their people. Studying the similarities and differences between English and Uzbek fairy tales helps to understand the uniqueness of each culture and develops communication and cooperation between peoples. Fairy tales are interesting and useful not only for children, but also for adults, and play an important role in strengthening their relationships.

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